

AN INTEGRATIVE APPROACH TO TEACHING ENGLISH IN NON-LINGUISTIC UNIVERSITIES

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Abstract: This article explores the challenges of integrating language learning into the educational processes of non-linguistic higher educational institutions. Drawing on the experiences of leading foreign specialists, it examines the specific features of implementing integrated learning and highlights its potential benefits. Key factors that influence the effectiveness of this integrative approach are identified. The article discusses the main stages of the cognitive process in language learning, ranging from initial exposure to skill development and practical application. Special emphasis is placed on the presentation of educational material, which is vital for successful comprehension. One example given is the use of long reads in academic settings, which involve engaging with information from a British newspaper in English. This method enhances students' interest in their classes and motivates them to learn the language through authentic materials. Furthermore, it enables students to analyze and assimilate the studied content effectively, fostering a comprehensive understanding of the subject matter.

Keywords: integrative approach, cognitive process, skills.

The current stage of development of the system of teaching foreign languages in universities not only in our country but throughout the world is characterized by the rapid flow of information in many previously existing areas of knowledge, as well as the effective use of communication technologies in the educational process. At the same time, one of the main ways to resolve the problematic situation, which consists of the contradiction between the constantly growing flows of information and the lack of time to master it, many leading scientists in this direction see the process of merging related fields of knowledge into one subject integrity. This approach will allow students to achieve a high level of skills development both in professional-oriented activities and in foreign language speech activities. Due to the growing need for highly qualified specialists who can implement their professional skills in a foreign language, this approach is currently becoming increasingly relevant and in demand. This problematic situation occupies an important place in modern pedagogy and methods of teaching not only a foreign language but also other natural and humanitarian disciplines. Its relevance lies in the complexity of its implementation, as well as its versatility.

The first integrated English language teaching programs in Germany appeared in the 90s of the last century due to the dominance of the English language in international communication. Currently, integrated education in English is implemented in many educational institutions in Germany. Leading universities in this country such as Georg-August-Universität Göttingen and Universität Freiburg, which have a great international reputation, offer programs taught in English, allowing foreign students to study undergraduate and postgraduate degrees.

The results of researchers in this direction confirm that it is an important and meaningful addition to existing traditional foreign language teaching programs (Gebauer et al., 2023; Lasagabaster, 2008; Küppers & Trautmann, 2013; Gierlinger & Wagner, 2016). Such programs are aimed at introducing teaching of certain subjects in English into the educational process. For example, in Denmark the relative number of universities offering programs in English is almost 70%, in Turkey this figure reaches 94%. In Switzerland, almost all universities offer programs in English, and

therefore it is the place with the highest degree of penetration of English-language education. A comparative analysis shows that integrated learning is currently quite popular in European universities.

The need to apply this direction of training is based on the conceptual principles of state policy for the development of teaching foreign languages, including English in higher educational institutions of our country. The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to raise activities to popularize the study of foreign languages in the Republic of Uzbekistan to a qualitatively new level" dated May 19, 2021, emphasizes the importance of proficiency in a foreign language for expanding the educational and professional opportunities of trained personnel. Such an approach to the organization of vocational training in a foreign language in universities should contain the following factors that take into account a high level of professional knowledge and proficiency in a foreign language in teaching, as well as possession of certain pedagogical skills and abilities of integrated teaching of various disciplines.

It should be noted that among the most common areas of specialties where the main student disciplines are taught in English are the following: business, journalism, IT technology, diplomacy, psychology, sociology, and others. In this aspect, in our republic, the relative share of universities and institutes offering English-language education is constantly increasing every year. Applicants willingly enroll in them, preferring to study not only at prestigious higher educational institutions but also to have the opportunity to master their chosen profession in a foreign language and have a good chance of integrating into the world community.

The observed tendency to combine various subjects into one whole is being considered by scientists from numerous countries around the world. There are a large number of research works examining integrated content and language of instruction for future professional workforces in various specialties (Merino & Lasagabaster, 2017; McDougald, 2016; He & Lin, 2020). However, these studies focus on some elements of teaching English, such as composing an oral speech, introducing dialogue, presenting a prepared presentation, and others. This does not provide a full opportunity to use English to gain new knowledge in professional activities and communicate freely in English outside the integrated learning environment.

According to Minakov L. Yu, the two most significant groups can be distinguished in the content of training. The first of them is knowledge (Minakova, 2015). Knowledge is understood as mastery of linguistic material on various topics, the concept of methods and techniques of speech activity in a foreign language, and knowledge of the realities of national culture. The second is skills and abilities that are defined as speech skills: pronunciation, intonation, graphic, spelling, lexical, grammatical, and speech skills: listening, speaking, as well as reading and writing.

The research uses a systematic approach to studying the concept of integrated learning, as well as its significance in the development of foreign language speech activity. The concepts of an integrated approach in higher education are considered. The key components of an integrative approach to teaching a foreign language in non-philological areas, in particular in the specialty of journalism, are analyzed. Also, the factors of the integrative approach for effective and successful application in the educational process are considered. In particular, an integrative approach to teaching English in the educational process of higher educational institutions is considered, based on materials from English-language periodicals.

The use of an integrative approach in the educational process of non-philological universities is aimed at developing the professional competence of students utilizing a foreign language using interdisciplinary connections. The integrative approach involves an equal combination of related topics of taught disciplines, the study of which is interrelated. According to some experts (Xuan Li, 2024; Ruiz-Madrid & Fortanet-Gómez, 2022; Villabona & Cenoz, 2021; Bashirov et al., 2024), the integration of English language courses with specialized disciplines becomes feasible during the process of professionalizing the English language.

In general, a unique formula of the cognitive process should be applied to effective learning of a foreign language, leaning towards the dialectical law of development: from the level of familiarity to the level of understanding and practical use. In foreign language classes, after the stage of sensory cognition, the stage of abstract thinking should be provided.

Thus, an integrative approach to teaching English in the modern educational process of higher educational institutions, based on materials from English-language periodicals, is certainly becoming in demand and is very effective. Using such materials in the educational process allows you to critically evaluate the thematic data being analyzed and develop students' knowledge comprehensively.

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